

Abstract Sorting

Your entries in this form will guide abstract decisions, including acceptance as poster with lightning talk, acceptance as oral, or rejection. This workshop is for software, so abstracts focused on science topics should be rejected. Abstracts indicating relevance for the wider NASA community should be considered for an oral presentation. The spreadsheet is available [here](#).

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. Please copy in the titles of the abstracts you think should be REJECTED. Separate * each title with a SEMICOLON (;). If none, please enter 'None'.

3. In this question and those that follow, please indicate at least your three top * choices for potential ORAL presentations by copying the title of the talk as the answer to each question (one per question). Oral presentations will be longer than the lightning presentations.

Title of first choice:

4. Title of second choice: *

5. Title of third choice: *

6. Title of fourth choice:

7. Title of fifth choice:

8. Title of sixth choice:

9. Title of seventh choice:

10. Title of eighth choice:

11. Title of ninth choice:

12. Title of tenth choice:

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